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*Factors That Impact Hospitality Education:
A Case Study in Hong Kong Hospitality Bachelor Education During 2019 - 2021*

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Abstract

Hong Kong has faced many catastrophes in recent years, including the 2019 protest and the 2020 coronavirus illness "COVID-19." Hong Kong's higher education system was severely impacted as a result of the emergency lockdown and subsequent social exclusion policies (Marinoni, Land and Jensen, 2020).

Chapter 1 presents a research to evaluate the elements now impacting the influence of hospitality education by students and graduates confronting the catastrophic scenario of 2019 and 2020 in order to address future difficulties. Chapter 1 includes considerations of the study's background, a succinct explanation ⁷⁷ of the research problem and aim, research questions, and other study restricting or defining factors.

Chapter 2 provides support and identifies research gaps by delving into these supporting scenarios, which span both present and historical ideas and discoveries. The second chapter begins with a discussion of literature search strategies before going on to conceptual foundations, a critical assessment of the literature, and a description of the research techniques employed.

Chapter 3 discusses all of the sampling and research procedures, as well as the technique that was employed, which was a sequential exploratory mixed methods design. The result is presented in Chapter 4 along with data analysis and associated discoveries. Finally, in the final chapter, utilise the given data and information to determine the factor and associated variables.

As a result of this knowledge gap, the current article investigates the Protest and ¹ COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on hospitality education, particularly online educational delivery in Hong Kong. Researchers examined a real-world scenario from Hong Kong to see how hospitality students responded. The underlying actions of educators and the consequences for curriculum design are explored. The study's primary objective, however, is to call attention to the need for hospitality training during times of crisis.

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Chapter 1: Foundation of the Study

Coronavirus Disease affects the global healthcare system, then different social-distancing measures happen and are announced around the world (Centre for Health Protection, 2020).

Moreover, Chau (2021) noted that in the 2019 protest in Hong Kong, 10,250 people have been arrested since June 2019 in protest-related cases, and 2,500 of them had been prosecuted. Additionally, in the 2020 coronavirus disease “COVID-19” was infected in China, then Hong Kong, then all around the world, Hong Kong was the first epidemic area after the 2019 protest in Hong Kong, many businesses were dropped (Roxborough, 2021).

Hong Kong is facing different disasters including the 2019 protest and 2020 coronavirus disease “COVID-19”. The lockdown and social distancing measures immediately had an enormous impact on higher education in Hong Kong (Marinoni, Land and Jensen, 2020).

Chapter 1 outlines a study to determine the factors currently influencing the impact of hospitality education by students and graduates who are facing the catastrophic situation of 2019 - 2021 to meet the challenges in the future.

1.1 Background of the Study

In Hong Kong, many students need to change to use distance learning in the university and 32% of them were charged with property damage and riot, most of them could not continue to study in 2019 (Chan, 2021). After half a year of protest, coronavirus disease has happened in Hong Kong.

After the end of 2020, coronavirus disease affected 185 countries, 1,542,412,000 learners, which constitute 89.4% of total enrolled learners. More than half higher education institutes would have negative financial consequence, and the most common impact of COVID 19 has been the cancelling of international travel with 83% and the cancellation or postponement of scientific conferences with 81% and the scientific projects are at risk of not

being completed at a bit more than half (Marinoni, Land and Jensen, 2020).

In Hong Kong, students' learning is influenced by many social issues and disease problems. Roxborough (2021) showed that Lan Kwai Fong began in 1978 with the aim of transforming the surrounding area into a local version of Tokyo's Ginza district, and after 2000, it became one of the most famous drink and relax places and well-known tourist visit area in Hong Kong, but it has recently faced unprecedented calamity, especially the protests and Coronavirus Disease, Lan Kwai Fong become a dead city.

Moreover, social-distancing measures in 2020 including a ban on public gatherings and the suspension of face-to-face school classes etc. measurement, since that, most parties and weddings were closed, and the restaurant was the hardest hit area (Lau and Cheung, 2021). It influences the hotel and hospitality industry, also influenced hospitality's student face-to-face lesson and internship.

Furthermore, as the city's tourism-related firms struggled to thrive in the middle of the coronavirus pandemic, around 100 redundancies in the Shangri-La community (Cheng, 2020). Hong Kong's InterContinental hotel also lays off 500 employees as it embarks on a two-year renovation program (Leung and Tsang, 2020).

In the Coronavirus Disease period, hotel and tourism job recruitment dramatically declined, and layoff cases happened all over the world, the industry needed to use time to recover (Jiang and Wen, 2020). Most hotels also rejected hospitality students for their internship program in Hong Kong (Lau and Cheung, 2021).

In light of the above flaws, researching the factors that influence hospitality education in Hong Kong is critical, especially in 2019 - 2021, when many students have been influenced. Overall, this topic is important, necessary and valuable.

1.2 Problem Statement

According to the IAU Global Survey Report, more than 60% Classroom teaching has been replaced by distance teaching and learning in Asia, 36% the majority of activities have been halted, but the university is working on ways to continue teaching and learning via digital or self-study methods (Marinoni, Land and Jensen, 2020). Also, Hong Kong's largest teachers' union end of this year, many higher education students migrant to United Kingdom or Canada to continues their degree program, more than 82% of the institute in Hong Kong had been stop the course within 2 weeks in 2019 protest period, some universities were more worries such as the Hong Kong Polytechnic University or the Chinese University of Hong Kong, which is the major hospitality programs holder in Hong Kong (Lam, 2021).

The problem in this case, two major stakeholders include student and lecturer are very important. Student's learning process and outcome is affected by the teaching material and process, the learning outcome is based on the result. If mainly distance learning, less activities, less practice internship and all the communication adopt computer machines, student learning and their behaviour may change. Also, institute's staff and faculty who have acquired and tested new tools and systems to enable distant teaching and learning for the unexpected and unprepared situation, those problems will influence the hospitality's student learning. Figure 1 outlines the concept and problem framework.

Figure 1. Concept and problem framework.

This case study mainly focused on the problem of the factors which affect the learning process and outcome even the internship. The protest and coronavirus disease are just the background in this study.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to explore and measure the student learning process and outcome during 2019 - 2021, which have caused most accidents such as the 2019 Hong Kong Protest Movement and COVID-19 issues. The abundance of online study and lesson material may have an effect on the student's learning experience, practical competence, and even the learning result; this research will investigate this thoroughly.

A study focused on hospitality higher education students who are Post-high school students, it only focuses on bachelor degree. This case study would go into great detail to examine and assess the student learning process and outcomes over the last few years, and it would only be applicable to hospitality students, not tourism students. Figure 2 outlines the purpose of the planned study, there are three steps. First identify the factor that influences the student's learning process; After that is the learning outcome; Finally, identify those factors and review the problem.

Figure 2. Cognitive map of study to identify the factors influencing the Hong Kong hospitality higher education student's learning and outcome based in 2019 - 2021.

The goal of the study was to find out how students learn and outcome in the hospitality field during extreme situations like COVID and social protest.

Based on this understanding, can improve teacher and lecturer responses to the challenges currently facing COVID19 virus or any challenge in the future.

1.4 Hypothesis and/or Research Questions

The below aims and research questions are derived from the problem statement, concept and problem framework and the cognitive map of study in Figure 1 and 2. They are as follows:

Aims

Investigate how students learn and perform in the hospitality industry under severe conditions, as well as the variables that affect this.

Research Question

Research Question 1: What variables influence the learning process of hospitality bachelor education students in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

Research Question 2: What variables impacted the learning outcomes of hospitality bachelor education students in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

Research Question 3: What factors encouraged hospitality bachelor education graduates to work in this sector and find employment in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

⁸¹ Answers to the three research questions provided a greater understanding of the factors which affect a student's learning process, outcome and result based on these challenge years.

Hypothesis

‘H⁰’ Null Hypothesis #1: Based on each phase, there will be no factor or difference in the learning process between previous years and these present years in Hong Kong.

‘H^a’ Alternate Hypothesis #1: Based on each phase, there will be factor/s and variations in the learning process between previous years and these present years in Hong Kong.

‘H⁰’ Null Hypothesis #2: In Hong Kong, there will be no factor or variation in learning outcomes depending on each phase between previous years and these present years.

‘H^a’ Alternate Hypothesis #2: Based on each phase, there will be factor/s and variations in learning outcomes between previous years and these present years in Hong Kong.

‘H⁰’ Null Hypothesis #3: There will be no factor or difference in the ability of graduates to work in the sector and find employment in Hong Kong between previous and current years, depending on each phase.

‘H^a’ Alternate Hypothesis #3: There will be factors and variations in graduates' ability to work in the sector and find employment in Hong Kong between previous and current years.

The three hypotheses related to three research questions, ‘H⁰’ or ‘H^a’ will know on findings.

The above hypotheses and research questions provide a firm foundation for the broader purpose of the study.

1.5 Limitations and Delimitations

Limitations

The study approaches, case study, face-to-face interviews, and questionnaires each have their own limitations. Moreover, this case study is limited in Hong Kong and focused on hospitality's student, also limited with the bachelor degree. Furthermore, this case study focused on the hospitality, not the tourism aspect. Although this case study is based in Hong Kong, it is limited with some major hotel and tourism institutes like SHTM and VTC. Above limitations influenced the study comprehensive and overall study, and which is not controllable.

Delimitations

This case study will not study the teacher, parents or other stakeholder feelings and motivation. This study is mainly based on student and related learning issues. Of course, the lecturer or teacher improvement and teaching process like pedagogy were included in this study because of the relationship of learning process and outcome. But those issues were not the main study purpose. Finding out the factor which influenced the student in 2019 - 2021 was the main purpose.

⁹⁰ 1.6 Definition of Terms

COVID-19. ⁸ "Coronavirus Disease 2019" or "SARS-CoV-2" and refers to the outbreak of viral pneumonia cases arising in Wuhan, Hubei Province, since December 2019 (Centre for Health Protection, 2020).

¹⁸ **2019 Hong Kong Protests.** Also known as the Anti-Extradition Law Amendment Bill Movement, was a series of protests in Hong Kong in response to the introduction of the Fugitive Offenders amendment bill by the Hong Kong government. Began on 15 March 2019 to early 2020 (Leung, 2019).

Recent Years. The "Recent Year" in this paper mainly focuses on 2019 Hong Kong Protests and 2020 Coronavirus Disease". And the "Coronavirus Disease" also continues until now "2021".

Higher Education. The "Higher education" means after high school, which only focuses on bachelor degree. The sub-degree and postgraduates program does not include this case study.

²³ **PolyU.** The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, one of the top universities for hospitality programs in the world.

⁸⁹ **SHTM.** School of Hotel and Tourism Management based on ⁵ The Hong Kong Polytechnic University or The Chinese University of Hong Kong.

VTC. The Hong Kong Vocational Training Council, which includes Hong Kong Institute of Vocational Education, Hotel and Tourism Institute, Technological and Higher Education Institute of Hong Kong THEi etc. institutes.

HKCT. The Hong Kong College Technology.

HKMU. The Hong Kong Metropolitan University.

CUHK. The Chinese University of Hong Kong.

HKU-SPACE. Hong Kong University School of Professional and Continuing Education.

1.7 Nature of Study

In-depth interviews and questionnaires were used in this case study to determine a student's learning process and outcome, which is the mixed method with exploratory sequential design, using qualitative data to explore quantitative findings. Figure 3 outlines that.

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Figure 3. Sequential Exploratory Mixed Methods Design - Emphasis on the Quantitative Phase (Berman, 2017).

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The exploratory sequential mixed methods design is defined by an initial qualitative data collecting and analysis phase, followed by a quantitative data collection and analysis period, and finally by a phase of data integration or connecting from the two distinct strands of data (Berman, 2017).

This case study is a novel concept and new topic based in Hong Kong, using qualitative data collecting '3 samplings' will find out more information about the student learning process and outcome. Then, based on the information to explore quantitative research to answer the problem. Thus, exploratory sequential mixed methods are more suitable.

An in-depth examination of student feedback and the effect that leads to the acceptance of online learning is possible with such a study. After the interview, the quantitative aspects serve to provide a clear analysis of the result, and based on the result and feedback, the questionnaire will be designed and analysed.

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This research is based on a case study to analyse and focus in 2019 - 2021 Hong Kong, how protest or COVID-19 etc. issues were affecting hospitality student learning even graduate. Thus, this research is very useful and unique in the hospitality research field.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

⁵ A literature review is a collection of previously published works on a subject. In any case, a literature review is meant to provide the researcher, author, and audience a wide overview of the issue (Harris, 1998). A literature review is a scientific document that summarises existing knowledge. Literature reviews are used in almost every academic topic (John, 2013). Reviewing contemporary literature synthesis and critical analysis is vital.

2.1 Introduction

This research's literature review analyses the overall relevant information, from student study motivation, learning result, to hospitality non-face to face concerns, thoroughly. To do a complete examination of existing research and literature in the study target area, earlier work and textbooks were studied.

³⁵ The purpose of this study was to determine the factors that influence Hong Kong hospitality bachelor education during 2019 - 2021. To support this research, multiple learning theories and situational factors were considered. Such as *Behaviourist theories*.

2.2 Hong Kong Overall Education Situation

Hong Kong's education was first supplied by Protestant and Catholic missionaries who also provided social services. In 1843, Italian missionaries started providing British and Chinese children with boy-only education. Frederick Stewart arrived in Hong Kong in 1862 and became the first headmaster of Queen's College, the first school established and completely financed by the Hong Kong government (Sweeting, 1990).

The higher education institutions in Hong Kong classify:

- 1) UGC-funded universities which are the universities funded by the public and under the University Grants Committee;
- 2) Self-funded institutions which are higher education institutions that are self-funded;
- 3) Public institutions which are higher education institutions funded by the Hong Kong Government; And
- 4) Sub-degree institutions which are the higher education institutions for their academic awards up to sub-degree level

Most hospitality programs are from the public institutions and sub-degree institutions except SHTM from PolyU, HKMU and CUHK (Liz 2020).

Due to recent protests and pandemics, many Hong Kong students must convert to distance learning, and 32% were charged with property damage and riot, preventing them from continuing their studies in 2019. (Chan, 2021). The Hong Kong National Security Law came into effect on July 1, 2020, and many rich families emigrated to the West. Between July and November of that year, about 1,474 students left Hong Kong with their families, according to a survey of 100 schools (Didi, 2021).

Due to its experience with SARS in 2003, Hong Kong was able to react rapidly in COVID-19. People used face masks, the city's borders were closed, and COVID-19 fatalities remained low for months (Health Department in Hong Kong, 2020). Prior to the epidemic, online learning was used in higher education, but mostly asynchronously. Due to the pandemic, teachers and students in Hong Kong had to live-stream courses (Xiong et al., 2020). Long-term campus seclusion in Hong Kong has lasted over a year with little sign of

normalcy. Involvement of universities in social issues creates concerns. Campus closures and online learning let Hong Kong colleges react quickly to the COVID outbreak (Holiday and Postiglione, 2020).

While many campuses remain shuttered, colleges continue to operate. Instead, universities and colleges have had to swiftly adapt to new difficulties in order to maintain their basic responsibilities of teaching, research, and service. Some institutions have been able to make timely and sensible choices, but not all (Altbach and de Wit, 2020).

Holiday and Postiglione (2020) claim that faculty and students are missing out on physical interactions like brief encounters in academic hallways. In and out of class, students learn a lot from their peers at university. Hong Kong's universities had to reopen libraries and learning commons. Professors at a Hong Kong university used messaging apps to keep in touch with colleagues. Outside educators visiting schools to speak to students is prevalent in Hong Kong. Visiting professors often give brief talks at universities. Hong Kong universities host regional and international conferences, as well as other events. By 2020, all seminars and conferences must be webcast. Many colleges are also organising webinars to educate their communities about the global epidemic and its likely academic repercussions. Hong Kong universities reacted to the epidemic in one of three ways: control, support, or positioning. In university management, a crisis is an event that jeopardises the institution's staff, physical structure, or reputation (Coombs and Holladay, 2009).

The University of Hong Kong has suggested opening Master's programs to recent Bachelor's graduates from every department, since this would lead to more education and learning pathways for those students who are reluctant to enter the labour market or who have difficulty doing so. However, although postgraduate degree work, particularly Master's programs, is expected to see increased applications after university graduation, this is due to a peculiar quirk in students' behaviour. A significant explanation for this lies in the expectation that many recent grads are waiting for the economy to improve — thinking that an extended period of joblessness now is better than waiting until later to go back to school (Lee et al., 2020). Overall, Hong Kong higher education, especially the hospitality field, is facing a big crisis.

2.3 Hong Kong Hospitality Education Situation

Hong Kong was a heterogeneous society born from history and financial achievement. Capitalism thrives in the city, with a bustling financial and retail industry. This neighbourhood has become a worldwide magnet for foreigners, resulting in the world's most expensive real estate. Unemployment is low and poverty is high in Hong Kong, despite the economic growth. The Hong Kong government has just lately begun to confront the expanding social and economic inequality (Oxfam Hong Kong, 2018).

Hong Kong hospitality education since the 1990s, the PolyU SHTM and VTC IVE were the beginner higher educational pioneer, PolyU provides Bachelor to Master degree, now they are providing Doctor of Philosophy 'Ph.D.' and Doctor of Hotel and Tourism Management 'D.HTM' programme. Additionally, CUHK, THEi and HKMU also provide Bachelor degrees for hospitality. Also, HKCT, IVE, YMCA-COC, HKU-SPACE and HTI provide diploma level to Higher Diploma in hospitality management aspects (Lo, 2005).

Following the protest and the COVID-19, it is having an unprecedented effect on both our personal lives and the economy. The risk of infection may be reduced by avoiding close contact with others during an epidemic. Furthermore, the education sector has suffered as a result of the protest and epidemic owing to school closures. Luckily, since the 2003 SARS epidemic, hospitality educators have adjusted their reaction measures to the unknown pandemic scenario and are doing their utmost to keep the educational system running. As a result, hospitality and tourism education is now mostly delivered online rather than in traditional classrooms. Many educational activities, such as seminars and workshops, are now conducted online in order to save time and money (Ye and Law, 2020).

In a poll done at a Hong Kong university, just 26% of students were happy with their online learning experiences, and more than 60% said that online courses were less successful than face-to-face courses in terms of learning efficacy. Whether online learning and teaching will eventually replace face-to-face sessions in higher education is a hotly debated topic (Xiong et al., 2020). As a result of the potential for online communication techniques to impact psychological distance between individuals, delivering educational content through the internet presents a problem for instructors and students establishing relationships (Darke et

al., 2016). Tavitiyaman et al. (2021) discovered that hospitality students had a harder time staying engaged and empathising while studying online. As a consequence of their nice personalities being hindered when hospitality students attend online courses, they lack social skills and experience significant levels of academics.

The goal of this paper is to get more academics and industry practitioners engaged in hospitality education research and to come up with solutions for similar crises in the future. The shift from offline to online education delivery, as well as a flexible internship arrangement and assessment, should be given attention apart from adopting reaction measures to minimise the risk of infection with COVID-19 and protest among associated educational personnel and students.

2.4 COVID and Protest affect Hospitality Education

COVID-19

The COVID-19 economic crisis, which threatened the world's economy and culture, killed almost 2 million people. Globally, 2.89 million people will die by 2021, according to the University of Washington's Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (Cortez, 2021). On April 1, 2020, 185 countries closed schools and higher education institutions, affecting 1,542,412,000 pupils, or 89.4% of total registered students. Some countries started relaxing confinement rules in early May, noting a drop in sickness and deaths. However, as of May 7, 177 schools and universities were still closed, affecting 1 268 164 088 pupils, or 72.4% of all enrolled students (Marinoni, Land and Jensen, 2020).

The COVID-19 impacted most businesses in Hong Kong, mainly hotels (Leung and Tsang, 2020). Many hotels in the area are facing bankruptcy due to political upheaval in 2019 and a coronavirus epidemic in 2020. The coronavirus epidemic wrecked havoc on Hong Kong's hotel industry, forcing room revenue to drop (Jim, 2020). Travel limitations forced some hotels to drastically adjust operations in the recent year. These continuous changes will have a substantial impact on sales and reduce operational team and staff needs (Cheng, 2020).

Due to the introduction of social distancing laws as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, many schools and institutions in Hong Kong have switched from offline to online education (Houlden and Veletsianos, 2020). Even after the COVID-19 epidemic, online learning may continue. Online programs, on the other hand, have been a big problem for hospitality students who are used to being in a real classroom. Understanding the link between students' personality characteristics, anxiety, perceptions of online learning, and student happiness is therefore critical for the continuing development of online learning in hospitality education (Tavitiyaman et al., 2021). Due to the current epidemic, learning has migrated from face-to-face to online, resulting in a lack of close-contact and physical connection.

PROTEST

On March 29, 2019, the political tensions were made public when Hong Kong's Chief Executive published a measure in the legislature that would allow Hong Kong citizens to be extradited to mainland China to face criminal charges. After the announcement, rallies and protests have both been calm and violent. Despite the withdrawal of the law, the protest movement, known for its rallying cry of "five demands," continued. Many of the protests were accompanied by acts of violence, including injuries, arrests, extensive use of tear gas, and assaults (Jung et al., 2021).

"A prison" on the university campus went from being a "war zone" when police fired tear gas and water cannons, and students retaliated with stones, arrows, and petrol bombs as reported in a newspaper story. After some time, the protestors were captured by the security forces. During this time, the other schools that were impacted suffered extensive harm, and they all had to close down in October of 2019 for online courses before COVID-19 appeared. And the most influential college is SHTM, which is the major and famous hotel and hospitality college in the world (Siu et al., 2019).

OVERALL

Typically, hospitality teachers often use face-to-face teaching methods that include talks, personal contacts, and internships. Lectures, debates, field excursions, guest lectures, panels/symposia/fora, small group activities, games or simulations, student presentations, case studies, demonstrations, and experiments are examples of these methods (Smith et al., 2019). However, in recent years, the pandemic changed this industry, and it is difficult to adapt.

In any online learning activity, hospitality students have less experience with engagement and empathy. When hospitality students take online classes, their pleasant personalities are hampered, and they don't know how to get along with people, resulting in high levels of learning, technical, and financial anxiety (Tavitiyaman et al., 2021).

It's no secret that online learning is commonplace in the hospitality industry's

education sector. Hospitality instructors have plenty of experience teaching on online platforms, including theory, laboratory, and practical courses. But not everyone is familiar with the whole online teaching approach. The vast majority of instructors have no idea how to deal with this sudden shift (Maslen, 2020).

All stakeholders are under stress while they participate in COVID-19 online learning. Students do not have computers or laptops, nor do they have data roaming cards for Wi-Fi access. This lack of resources might impede your ability to study effectively online. In the meanwhile, teachers are under pressure to complete assessment assessments, make logistics preparations, and prepare (Wong, 2020). Even while we've seen benefits such as education, research, and information exchange via the Internet, we now know more about its boundaries and acknowledge that it is not a cure-all (Jung et al., 2021).

Additionally, a lot of Hong Kong's college graduates spend more time than others finding full-time employment, and they also earn less money when they finally do. A recent report by major job sites says that the number of jobs available in Hong Kong would decrease by 55% as a result of the crisis sparked by the demonstrations and the pandemic (Chan, 2020).

2.5 Theory of Learning

¹⁷ Theories of Learning include behaviourist theories, cognitive psychology, constructivism, social constructivism, experiential learning etc. concept and philosophy. Behaviourist theories, social constructivism and experiential learning concepts are most related to the hospitality student learning situation due to the practical and experience request.

The atmosphere and locality influenced students' learning experiences, according to behavioural theories. The central tenet of behaviourism is that learning includes making connections between environmental stimuli and observable reactions (Kosky and Allan, 2004).

¹⁷ Measurable behavioural changes interest behaviourists. Following a good rewarding result, a response to a stimulus is reinforced by exercise and repetition, according to renowned behaviourist thinker Thorndike. This is akin to “drill-and-practice” tactics. ¹⁷ Skinner, another notable behaviourist established “operant conditioning”. He thinks rewarding accurate components of a more complex behaviour reinforces and encourages recurrence. In this case, ¹⁷ reinforcers ensure that the desired partial behaviours occur. To learn is to approximate the intended partial behaviours gradually or sequentially using reward and punishment. Experiential learning theories, on the other hand, are based on social and constructivist learning theories, but emphasise experience. They want to discover how first-hand or second-hand experiences inspire and motivate children to learn. As a result, learning involves experiencing significant life experiences that affect one's knowledge and behaviour (Dumont et al., 2010).

Less face-to-face learning may affect the situation of the “drill-and-practice” method. How distance learning in the hospitality theme could improve the reward and punishment system is a big issue and concern. Less face-to-face social is it equal to less experiential learning, based on the theory? We all know whether first-hand or second-hand is not the big issue, how to do meaningful learning experiences as an important matter. Schleicher (2020) stated that hospitality students need comprehensive learning experience, especially practical skills like internship, otherwise the student graduate will find the job difficult. Less face-to-face, less communication with the classmates also affects the communication skills.

Moreover, in contrast to cognitive learning, which is academic information such as vocabulary acquisition, Rogers emphasised the significance of experiential learning, which is about the application of knowledge. Experiential learning, according to Rogers, meets the needs and desires of individuals and is linked to personal transformation and progress (Rogers, 1969).

Kolb (1984) presented the four-stage cyclic process, and the four stages are namely Concrete Experience, Reflection, Abstract Conceptualisation, and Active Experimentation. He also related experiential learning and learning styles. He emphasises how differences in individual personalities and learning preferences might lead to a preference for a specific stage of the stage. Figure 4 outlines that.

Figure 4. The Four-Stage Cyclic Process

According to Kolb (1984) and Rogers (1969), teachers ensure that activities are designed and carried out in ways that offer each learner the chance to engage in the manner that suits them best, especially outgoing activities. Less face-to-face and seldom communication will affect the student learning process. Students need internship and practice skills rather than stay at home and use Zoom to study (Baber, 2020). Pupils control their own learning in the online method, which increases their sense of responsibility.

However, this set-up may be harmful to ²students who have trouble managing their time and energy. Anxiety over online learning is becoming more common as a result of the impact of fear on pupils (Wombacher et al., 2017). ²Students with high levels of neuroticism, for example, may lack the courage to voice their thoughts in an online forum. While this is going on, students who are frequently considered inactive in a traditional classroom may now actively share their thoughts online. There are other variables that contribute to the related worries, such as ²the level of Internet dependability, security of the online platforms, and possible loss in student attentiveness (Bao, 2020).

2.6 Synthesis and Critical Analysis of Recent Literature

More than a thousand studies on COVID-19 will be conducted by 2020. A study of relevant literature sources, with the majority of the research focusing on how COVID-19 impacted student learning. Although academics have attempted to extend the literature on hospitality and tourism education by reviewing its development in several countries (Goh and King, 2019), this study is different; it focuses on COVID-19 and Protest, two subjects that impacted students' learning over a period of time, not just one year.

Some of the literature is quite close to my subject. For example, Liz (2020) explores how most students in recent years facing the protest and COVID-19 pandemic problem, lost their Hong Kong citizen identification and the learning interest.

Jung et al. (2021) found that online and distant learning is not an effective teaching method in the future since students cannot completely grasp everything, and it is also impossible to manage the student properly online, with the greatest pressure coming from the parents.

Wong (2020) also discovered students who are unable to afford computers and laptops, as well as data roaming cards for Wi-Fi access, are more likely to struggle when studying online.

The preceding study is based on a review and critique of general studies, which examine and critique the online learning challenge, as well as societal problems such as pandemics that have impacted the whole education sector. It is not complete since it uses the idea of learning motivation to evaluate the problem, and it is also not studied at all levels; it is concentrated on the high school and bachelor's level. Nowadays, the majority of master's and doctorate degrees are delivered through online and distance education. Those papers were not entirely opposed to them.

Numerous experts have examined behaviourist theories, social constructivism, and experiential learning concepts in the context of learning process theory. These studies are beneficial because they help us identify the variables that have influenced the learning

process and results of hospitality students in previous years.

In the research, Baber (2020) explained students don't have a lot of face-to-face interaction, they are less likely to be fully engaged in their education, they are less motivated for learning.

Wombacher et al. (2017) investigate online learning, it may have the unintended consequence of making students' time management and energy levels difficult to manage, and students have exacerbated anxieties about online learning.

The majority of research is based on Kolb and Rogers' (1969) "Four-stage cyclic process" and behaviourist theories such as "Drill-and-practice" techniques. These theoretical ideas are beneficial and really assist both student motivation and environmental variables. However, it is based on broad research, not on hospitality. Hospitality management topics are often combined with tourism and referred to as hotel management degrees. These programs include extensive communication and internships to acquire practical skills and experiences in areas such as front line, catering, and housekeeping. Thus, this article is unusual in that it focuses on hospitality and motivation, and it is a Hong Kong-based study. Protest and pandemic issues are so prevalent in the globe today that this case study will serve as a reference for analysing and forecasting the issue.

2.7 Summary

In Conclusion, because of the well-publicised political, social, and cultural tensions in Hong Kong, the city was particularly severely affected. Hong Kong suffered turmoil during the start of the pandemic as a result of these circumstances, which was unlike anywhere else in the globe. There was a tremendous lot of uncertainty and anguish ⁶⁴ as a result of the pandemic, which persisted throughout the experience.

Despite the fact that Hong Kong academics and universities were prepared to deal with the SARS outbreak, the pandemic caused even greater concern, anxiety, and sadness among the general public and academic institutions.

The current influenza epidemic, on the other hand, has presented new difficulties to academics, including a decreased capacity to educate effectively and properly interact with stakeholders. The majority of academics are already adopting new academic methods, although a minority are still finding it difficult to adjust to their new work environment.

Furthermore, a study of the literature showed that there is relatively little research particularly connected to writing about the variables that influence hospitality higher education, especially in recent years. According to the findings, COVID-19 is a novel subject for the study area, and most studies have distinct focus points. Although the preceding study has its own characteristics, benefits, and drawbacks, and also aids me in developing a framework, this research is unique and distinct from the preceding research. While this study has many limitations, it delivers in important ways.

Primary qualitative interviews are used to conduct qualitative case studies. As secondary research, the questionnaire is intended to discover variables that affect the learning process and results of hospitality higher education students, as well as factors influencing their employment after graduation. As well ⁷¹ as conducting interviews with current students in the study focus organisation, additional face-to-face interviews are conducted with current students in the institute to learn about their perceptions of the situation and the factors they consider important in how they learn and give feedback.

Chapter 3: Methodology

This study focused on the topic of the overall Hong Kong education situation and the specific influence that affects hospitality education in 2019 - 2021. ⁶¹ The purpose of the research study was to investigate how students learn and perform in the hospitality industry under severe conditions, as well as the variables that affect this. For the case study, as Yin (2018) stated, case studies are chosen when relevant behaviours can't be altered and a current event or series of occurrences are being studied.

The study design, target population, sampling technique, sample, instruments, quality of evidence, data collecting procedures, data analysis procedures, researcher function, and protection of participants are all discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Research Design

The research design is a single case study of Hong Kong hospitality bachelor education during 2019 - 2021. The exploratory sequential mixed methods design was used, beginning with the initial qualitative data collecting 'In-depth interview', then followed by a quantitative data collection 'Questionnaire'. Then, there will be a stage of integrating or linking the two different data streams (Berman, 2017). The interview is the supportive method and the questionnaire is the main method that answers the research question and hypothesis.

⁷² The main purpose is to use exploratory sequential mixed methods design due to lack of information even in Literature review, it is difficult to identify sufficient measurement variables from the Literature review for designing survey questionnaires. Thus, exploring the information from the interviewee, collecting the data and then exploring the extra variables or exploring new information, which is a more suitable way (Creswell, Plano Clark, Gutmann, and Hanson, 2003).

There are several advantages to conducting an in-depth interview. For example, interviewers may observe differences in tone and word choice to get a more in-depth understanding of the topic matter. When compared to other methods of data collection, the sample has a higher

degree of quality than the other methods. The fact that in-depth interviews have the potential to be so insightful means that they may provide incredibly beneficial findings relatively quickly when they are conducted (Yin, 2018).

45 Now that we've identified a few of the most prominent interview designs accessible to qualitative researchers, we can look more carefully at several options for conducting qualitative interviews depending on the research available. 10 These recommendations are intended to equip the researcher with the tools necessary to conduct a well-structured, professional interview with their subjects. According to Creswell (2003; 2007), some of the most prevalent material discovered in the literature connected to interviews includes the preparation for the interview, the development of appropriate research questions, and the actual execution of the interview.

The preparation and the details of the interview will show in the next part. In light of the fact that they are under supervision, certain inquiries should provide guidance to steer them in the appropriate way. 66 If this is not the case, the interview will not yield useful information (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). As a result, most of the questions in this interview have already been developed, with the exception of the final question, which is open-ended.

In-depth Interview

Overall, the interview is designed for teachers and students who are teaching and learning in hospitality and must be Post-high school education. The samples of the interview are only three because it is not the main data analysis, the interview is mainly for exploring the information or variables, so choosing three is enough. Also, 'Purposive Sampling' will be used, purposive 26 sampling is a sampling approach in which the researcher chooses individuals of the population to participate in the study based on his or her own judgement rather than the assessment of others. 60 Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling strategy that happens when "items picked for the sample are chosen by the researcher based on his or her opinion." (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). The interview has two stages: Introductions and open-ended questions. The interview period depends on the information.

Questionnaire

It is intended for students to complete the questionnaire. Samples contain 100 elements, and this is the most common method of directly discovering the study questions and identifying the variables. The next section explains the rationale for selecting a sample size of 100 people. Furthermore, the questionnaire will be administered using the Google form online platform, and all of the information will be saved. There are four parts to the questionnaire: introductions, RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3. The questionnaire is divided into four sections. About the sampling process and procedure, sampling selection and sampling identification will show below.

3.2 Sampling

The target population for this study included 3 hospitality teachers or students for an interview and 100 hospitality students and teachers for a questionnaire. They don't know each other, interviewees and questionnaire samples are different. For students, all the samples must be hospitality bachelor students in Hong Kong and study after or subsequent to 2019.

This study used Purposive sampling with a purposeful "Extreme or Deviant case" sample procedure for an interview and Random Selection for a questionnaire survey. Using extreme or deviant case samples, researchers pick examples that are uncommon or distinctive in some sense, such as those who have achieved spectacular success or suffered a significant failure. This deliberate sampling technique may assist the study in a number of ways, most notably in exploring the breakthrough (Patton, 1989).

For the random sampling picking numbers, it is ideal for less than the whole population of 10 per cent owing to the representative and finding the variable of the inquiry (Conroy, 2018). If we assume that each university is similar, there are approximately 500 to 600 students studying the major hospitality studies in Hong Kong with five major programmes. This does not include the tourism program and the combined program. According to the VTC report of students data 2020, the program received approximately 100 to 120 applications in hospitality studies. If you include the combined program, which is more than four programs, you'll have an additional 400 participants. The most relevant and fair number of students to sample is 1000 students with a 10 percent error rate, which is 100 students.

Random Selection refers to the fact that each individual in a population has an equal probability of being chosen. The approach for selecting candidates is based on a random process. The random process is only for Bachelor degrees with 100 samples. For these students, there have 4 Bachelor's programmes in relevant subjects are there which are:

- 1) HKU SPACE - Bachelor of Science (Honours) Hospitality Management via University of Plymouth;
- 2) PolyU's School of Hotel and Tourism Management - BSc (Hons) in Hotel Management programme;

- 3) PolyU's ⁸ School of Professional Education and Executive Development - BA (Hons) in Hospitality Management; and
- 4) ²³ The School for Higher and Professional Education (SHAPE) - BSc (Hons) International Hospitality Business Management via Sheffield Hallam University

CUHK STHM is a well-known program. However, it is a combined curriculum with a focus on real estate development. As a result, CUHK is excluded from the sample.

In addition, 100 samples have 25 students from HKU SPACE; 25 students from PolyU's SHTM; 25 students from PolyU's SPEED and 25 students from SHAPE.

Each school had observed the email information and had made the random pick based on that information. Those emails were kept confidential by the institute. Concerning confidentiality in private, the information is provided below. The sample is chosen at random via email, and the students submit their work online. For the method and technique that has previously been identified, as well as for the cooperation with each school. Email is an efficient and accurate method of identifying and contacting the sampling.

3.3 Instrumentation

Interview

Below is a breakdown of the research questions ⁶⁷ and how they relate to the questionnaire questions:

Research Question 1: What variables influence the learning process of hospitality higher education students in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

Interview Question 1: What are your thoughts on hospitality students acquiring knowledge?

Interview Question 3: Do you believe that online learning platforms benefit hospitality students?

Interview Question 4: Are you currently pursuing any internships or activities, and do you believe they are necessary for hospitality studies?

Interview Question 5: Do you believe that instructors or lecturers educate effectively?

Research Question 2: What variables impacted the learning outcomes of hospitality higher education students in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

Interview Question 1: What are your thoughts on hospitality students acquiring knowledge?

Interview Question 3: Do you believe that online learning platforms benefit hospitality students?

Interview Question 4: Are you currently pursuing any internships or activities, and do you believe they are necessary for hospitality studies?

Interview Question 5: Do you believe that instructors or lecturers educate effectively?

Research Question 3: What factors encouraged hospitality higher education graduates to work in this sector and find employment in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

Interview Question 6: Do you believe that after finishing your program, the student would have an easy time finding work in this industry?

Interview Question 7: You think how many students will pursue careers in this field after graduation?

Other or Open-ended Question:

Interview Question 2: How many times do you study on online platforms? (General Question)

Interview Question 8: Anything you'd want to share in relation to this subject? (Open Question)

Selective Question: Normally, for the starter. (Open Question)

Prefield sessions (interviewing the investigator) and online testing of the study supported and changed the given research question breakdown as needed ⁶⁸ to ensure that the questions matched the study's goals and allowed for complete participant replies while reducing possible researcher bias.

Questions with an open-ended answer Participants' answers to questions 2 , 8 and selective questions were intended to be a discussion starter and a way to gather basic participant data, not essential to the study's design.

Prefield and online testing were done on the opening interview questions to see whether they were conversation starters and provided useful information (all ⁸²interview questions can be found in Appendix A).

Each question related to some of the literature review and concepts, which is shown below:

1. Q1 related to Chan, 2021; Tavitiyaman et al., 2021; Darke et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2019; Maslen, 2020; Dumont et al., 2010; Schleicher, 2020; Wombacher et al., 2017.
2. Q2 related to Xiong et al., 2020; Holiday & Postiglione, 2020; Ye and Law, 2020; Darke et al., 2016; Tavitiyaman et al., 2021; Houlden and Veletsianos, 2020; Jung et al., 2021; Wombacher et al., 2017.
3. Q3 related to Xiong et al., 2020; Holiday & Postiglione, 2020; Ye and Law, 2020; Darke et al., 2016; Tavitiyaman et al., 2021; Houlden and Veletsianos, 2020; Smith et al., 2019; Jung et al., 2021; Bao, 2020; Baber, 2020; Wombacher et al., 2017.
4. Q4 related to Holiday & Postiglione, 2020; Smith et al., 2019; Maslen, 2020; Schleicher, 2020; Rogers, 1969; Baber, 2020.
5. Q5 related to Altbach & de Wit, 2020; Ye and Law, 2020; Smith et al., 2019; Maslen, 2020; Wombacher et al., 2017.
6. Q6 related to Coombs & Holladay, 2009; Lee et al., 2020; Lo, 2005; Jim, 2020; Leung and Tsang, 2020; Cheng, 2020; Chan, 2020; Schleicher, 2020.
7. Q7 related to Altbach & de Wit, 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Jim, 2020; Leung and Tsang, 2020; Cheng, 2020; Chan, 2020; Schleicher, 2020.
8. And Q8 is an open-ended question.

Questionnaire

Following the in-depth interview, the questionnaire examines the information and factors gleaned from the interview data and makes recommendations. A direct response to the study question and hypothesis is provided by the questions in the questionnaire. The questionnaire design is based on the information gathered during the interview, however it is divided into three sections, each section of which is connected to the research questions and investigating the findings.

Three components are included in the questionnaire, which is a paper questionnaire. Part A is connected to RQ 1 'Learning Process'. Part B is connected to RQ 2 'Learning Outcomes,' and Part C, on the other hand, is connected to RQ 3 'Employment Factor'; those parts have covered the variables of the interview. In Parts A to C of the questionnaire, the four-point Likert scale was utilised since there is no neutral alternative available. If there were a neutral option, the sample that answered the question while they were thinking would be affected (Vagias and Wade, 2006). The questionnaire uses a four-point Likert scale, with 1 representing strongly disagree and 4 representing strongly agree. We will be able to determine their thoughts and direction based on the facts. However, not all questions are applicable to every sampling, so 5 is the N/A which means 'Not applicable'.

3.4 Data Collection Procedures

In-depth Interview

Stage 1: Introduction: Casual conversation, discussion of the study's subject and objective, and then review of their participation anonymously, as well as review and signing on the appropriate participant permission form. Finally, get permission to record and take notes.

Stage 2: Questionnaires should be administered as needed.

Stage 3: Begin with the opening questions and work your way through them sequentially: Provide a recording reminder and then begin the interview process by going through the introductory questions. Depending on the interview and prior interview replies, follow-up questions may be asked.

Stage 4: Reintroduce dialogue into the interview: Inquire if the participant has any other insights to contribute.

Stage 5: Concluding: Express gratitude for the participant's time, participation, and insights. Additionally, explain that they will get a transcript for approval prior to the study's findings being released.

Stage 6: Provide the participant with a copy of their transcript to review and amend or finalise as required, including a transcript approval letter 'Appendix A' in which participants are asked to contribute any new information or insights not covered during the interview.

Questionnaire

Stage 1: Introduction and familiarisation with the Privacy Ordinance by the samples (Personal data kept confidential).

Stage 2: All samples must confirm they are hospitality students in Hong Kong who study after or subsequent to 2019. And submit their personal information and CGPA.

Stage 3: Answer all the questions and submit.

Chapter 4: Finding

The research study's goal was to find out how students learn and perform in the hospitality sector when they are subjected to extreme circumstances, as well as the elements that influence their performance. For this chapter, we will go through the findings that were made following the inquiry; this section is mostly concerned with the analysis and the data that was collected.

The In-depth interview was performed by a total of three respondents, two of whom were students and one of whom was a teacher. The questionnaire was prepared after obtaining the information and factors. Following that, a total of 100 randomly selected respondents from various colleges or programs completed the questionnaire, with a 100 percent response rate.

4.1 Participant Demographics

According to the demographic features of the respondents, which are shown in Table 1, it was discovered that 100 respondents (39 percent) were male and (61 percent) were female, with the majority of respondents (100 respondents) being female.

In terms of age, 54 percent were under the age of 21, 26 percent were under the age of 22, and the remaining 20 percent were of a different age. In terms of nationality, 81 percent of respondents were from Hong Kong, 11 percent were from China, 3 percent were from the United Kingdom, and the remaining respondents were from France, the United States, South Korea, and Japan, among other countries.

The majority of respondents begin their studies in 2021 (41 percent) or 2020 (33 percent), and their program concludes in 2022 (56 percent), 2021 (17 percent), or 2023 (13 percent) (13 percent). 100 people responded, with 27 percent coming from VTC SHAPE, 26 percent coming from PolyU SPEED, 23 percent coming from PolyU SHTM, and 24 percent coming from HKU SPACE, respectively.

Additionally, we will observe that the majority of overseas replies came from PolyU SHTM, which included all of the United Kingdom, the United States, South Korea, and other nations.

Table 1. Demographic Features of the Respondents

Demographic Characteristic	Frequency & Percentage %	St Dev. (σ)
<u>Gender</u>		
Male	39	
Female	61	
<u>Age</u>		
		20.29449843
19	6	
20	9	
21	54	
22	26	
23	4	
24	1	
<u>Institute</u>		
		1.825741858
VTC SHAPE	27	
PolyU SPEED	24	
PolyU SHTM	23	
HKU SPACE	26	
<u>Nationality</u>		
		29.77135088
Hong Kong	81	
Mainland China	11	
France	1	
United Kingdom	1	
United States	1	
South Korea	2	
Japan	1	
<u>Period from</u>		
		16.02081979
2018	4	
2019	22	
2020	33	
2021	41	
<u>Period to</u>		
		20.57911563

2021	17
2022	56
2023	13
2024	8
2025	6

For the three respondents of the interviewee, Mr Daniel Ho, Mr Sam Wong and Dr Ricky Chan, their details and information were shown in appendix A.

4.2 Result of Interview and Extra Variables

Following the interview data, the three responders of the interviewee supplied some thoughts and concepts, which will be transferred to the topic of the questionnaire survey once the data has been analysed. Furthermore, that information may have an impact on the variables in the study. Those factors will be considered in the formulation of the research questions.

RQ1: What variables influence the learning process of hospitality higher education students in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

The learning process may be impacted by a variety of elements, including the setting, atmosphere, instructor teaching style and approach, and the student's internal characteristics, which respondent Sam (Interview A3) provides as examples of laziness and inability to concentrate on online work for RQ1.

RQ2: What variables impacted the learning outcomes of hospitality higher education students in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

In RQ2, the learning result is one of the most challenging elements to study since the outcome might be a practical skill and information gained from the course, as well as an attitude and style, among other things. If they have excellent test scores and learn quickly, but dislike engagement and conversation with others, it is possible that they may have a less than satisfactory result when they work outside the classroom. Similarly to what Daniel said

(Interview A1), the conclusion is depleting the individuals who believe that in recent years we have thought a lot about online learning, but it might be an issue of learning mentality.

RQ3: What factors encouraged hospitality higher education graduates to work in this sector and find employment in Hong Kong in 2019 - 2021?

In RQ3, the element that promotes the students or graduates to work in this business, includes income, sociality, and the market. Just as Dr. Ricky (Interview A2) indicated, following the crisis of the virus and protest, most hospitality students work another employment and career. And Sam (Interview A3) remarked, aside from the salary and market, there is the aspect of future trends, some of the students may like Sam to wait for the market to open when the virus is gone. This means the factors include Personal mindset, sociality and related benefits. Thus, according to the above interview materials and information, we simplify and categorise the causes with 3 majority sections, which include:

- A) Environment (Atmosphere, Place, Learning Platform, Sociality);
- B) Humanity (Friends, Classmates, Teachers, Instructors, Family, Human Being);
- C) Personal Mindset (Attitude, Discipline, Observation, Understanding).

The external variables A and B were identified, and the internal component C will be identified. Following the categorization, we will investigate each section to see if there are any characteristics or variables that cause the data to be different or aberrant. That is the element that each RQ will be searching for. And the major part is to investigate the H0 or Ha to fulfil the RQ and aims.

4.3 Result of Questionnaire

In the questionnaire, part A is for RQ1; B is for RQ2 and C is for RQ3.

Category Comparison

In Part A, questions 1, 3, 13, 15, 16, 17, and 18 are categorised as belonging to Personal Mindset; Questions 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 19, and 20 are categorised as belonging to Humanity; Questions 2, 10, 11, 12, 14 are categorised as belonging to the Environment.

Part B, questions 21, 22, 28, and 32 are categorised as belonging to Personal Mindset; Questions 25 and 34 are categorised as belonging to Humanity; Questions 23, 24, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, and 33 are categorised as belonging to the Environment.

Part C, questions 35, 39, and 42 are categorised as belonging to Personal Mindset; Questions 40, 41 and 43 are categorised as belonging to Humanity; Questions 36, 37, and 38 are categorised as belonging to Environment.

General Comparison

The majority of the questions in the questionnaire will be positive, and we will review the feedback of that category in each RQ, especially the Mean, Standard Deviation, and the t-Test to compare three groups of students who answer yes and no with the Q44, Q45, and Q46 to determine whether the Hypothesis needs to be rejected. H_0 denotes no factor or difference, while H_a denotes an alternative. Except for the category comparison, we will evaluate the overall respondents who believe RQ 1 to 3 needs the hypothesis to be rejected. If there is no need to reject, we will examine the link between the two groups (Yes & No), what they believe, and what elements or variables have changed. Overall general comparison is mainly to find out the H_0 and H_a and find the different variables. Category comparison is mainly for discovering the factors which affect each RQ. Those respondents have mentioned their CGPA in the questionnaire, the Q45 will compare with the CGPA also.

It is critical to examine whether or not there is a substantial variation in the 'Mean' number between Yes and No in Q44 through Q46. Because these difficulties have an effect on the outcome and emotion, they have an effect on the analysis.

It was unable to conduct in-depth analysis of the data using the 'Mean' since two distinct groups were independent. Thus, to determine the significance of a difference, the t -test is an excellent tool for examining the significance of a difference between two sets of data, since it allows for easy comparison of both sides.

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{s_{\Delta}}$$
$$s_{\Delta} = \sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}$$

This is the formulation of t - value where \bar{x} is the sample mean, s is the sample standard deviation and n is the sample size.

Following a review of the questionnaire, there were a total of 100 responders, with all data listed in 4.1 Participant Demographics. According to the findings of Q44 to Q46, the Q44 linked to RQ1 has 84% Yes and 16% No; the Q45 related to RQ2 has 75% Yes and 25% No; and the Q46 connected to RQ3 has 95% Yes and 5% No. The comparison will show in the next section.

4.4 Results of Data Analysis

In the research question focal areas, an examination of the data gathered through the research questions revealed a plethora of varied replies based on the data analysis. This section will discover the varied replies data from RQ 1 to RQ3.

4.4.1 Research Question 1

Summary of Part A

There are three data points for the summary in the questionnaire section A 'Related to RQ1'. They are as follows:

- 1) Table 2 contains general statistics;
- 2) Table 3 has data on each institution; and
- 3) Table 4 contains data on each responder.

Table 2: General Data (Part A)

	Humanity	Environment	Personal Mindset
Mean	2.93	2.97	2.38
Std. Deviation	0.27	0.25	0.24
Minimum	2.4	2.2	1.9
Maximum	3.5	3.8	3
Kurtosis	-0.45	1.61	0.21

Table 3: Part A (RQ1) Box Plot of each Institute

Table 4: Part A (RQ1) Data of each Respondent

According to Table 2, the primary three components have been discussed earlier. The Mean of the personal thinking 2.38 was lower than humanity and the environment. The Standard Deviation was comparable and not large which suggests the data spread is concentrated. And the Kurtosis shows us the data shape and details, we will see the environment was the highest one with 1.61 (leptokurtic) and the Humanity is -0.45 (platykurtic), while they are similar Standard Deviation level.

Table 3 summarises the data pertaining to the discrepancies between the institutes. In terms of personal mindset, the majority of statistics are comparable, with the exception of PolyU Speed, which has the greatest maximum and median values, and the PolyU SHTM, which is much different. SHTM students are more concerned with humanity and the environment than with mindset. Alternatively, VTC SHAPE was more concerned with the environment, having a higher limit and being comparable to PolyU Speed. And table 4 shows the line chart of each respondent, we will see the environment was higher than the other, especially the online learning.

Comparison with two different groups (ROI)

The t - test will be used to compare two groups. The t -test, which uses a two-tailed analysis with a 95 percent confidence level, was used to assess $P(T \leq t)$ and determine whether or not to reject or accept H₀ 'Null Hypothesis' (H₀: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$; H_a: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$). Due to the fact that the two groups are distinct, it is unpaired. To demonstrate that the data is significant between the two groups, the two-tailed t test should be satisfied ($p < 0.025$). It is concerned with the question, "Is there a major difference between groups [Yes] and [No]?"

After the analysis (Table 5), five questions are significant ($p < 0.025$) and rejected H₀ (Null Hypothesis). Thus, the two groups have a significant difference.

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 Table 5: Two-Sample *t* Test Results (RQ1) ^a

Hypothesis: Is there a significant difference between a group "Yes" and the group "No" in RQ1 (Q44)? (H₀: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$; H_a: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)

Item	Mean (Yes ^b / No ^c)	P(T<=t) two-tail (p<0.025)
19 Question A1	2.71 ^b / 2.63 ^c	0.7088909632
Question A2	2.85 ^b / 3.19 ^c	<u>0.00855317127</u>
Question A3	2.21 ^b / 1.94 ^c	0.1943127868
Question A4	2.36 ^b / 2.13 ^c	0.2835067911
Question A5	3.14 ^b / 2.88 ^c	0.1551134406
Question A6	3.15 ^b / 3.13 ^c	0.8589313875
Question A7	3.01 ^b / 2.88 ^c	0.4143570283
Question A8	3.21 ^b / 2.81 ^c	0.05122751842
Question A9	2.85 ^b / 2.06 ^c	<u>0.00008425348487</u>
Question A10	3.14 ^b / 3.19 ^c	0.7226754795
Question A11	3.36 ^b / 3.25 ^c	0.4319918756
Question A12	2.40 ^b / 2.19 ^c	0.2512573409
Question A13	2.46 ^b / 2.44 ^c	0.8567047326
Question A14	3.14 ^b / 2.94 ^c	0.3509022918
Question A15	3.21 ^b / 3.06 ^c	0.2924014382
Question A16	2.81 ^b / 2.06 ^c	<u>0.000122060412</u>
Question A17	2.65 ^b / 2.56 ^c	0.6104543603
Question A18	3.12 ^b / 3.25 ^c	0.3518387245

Question A19	3.00 ^b / 3.00 ^c	1
Question A20	2.92 ^b / 2.88 ^c	0.665585132
Humanity	2.96 ^b / 2.72 ^c	<u>0.0007794136394</u>
Environment	2.98 ^b / 2.95 ^c	0.6818830812
Personal Mindset	2.40 ^b / 2.24 ^c	<u>0.01537907362</u>
¹¹ ^a Showing those items found to be significantly different.		
^b Total Sample Size = 84		
^c Total Sample Size = 16		

Those four questions are a significant difference (Rejected H₀) which is A2, A9, A16 and the Personal Mindset. A2 and A9 are both related to online and face-to-face learning comparison, A9 is the question about the teachers or lecturer's teaching style. A16 is about the learner's attitude compared with the classroom's atmosphere.

4.4.2 Research Question 2

Summary of Part B

There are three data points for the summary in the questionnaire section B, similar to Part A.

Table 6: General Data (Part B)

	Humanity	Environment	Personal Mindset
Mean	3.03	2.65	2.67
Std. Deviation	0.53	0.18	0.28
Minimum	1.5	2	2
Maximum	4	3	3.5
Kurtosis	0.25	0.38	0.42

Table 7: Part B (RQ2) Box Plot of each Institute

RQ2 (Each Institute Comparison)

Table 8: Part B (RQ2) Line Chart of each Respondent

According to Table 6, the primary three components have been discussed earlier. The Mean, Standard Deviation and Kurtosis of each category were similar, they are only leptokurtic. Table 7 also summarizes the data pertaining to the discrepancies between the institutes. In terms of humanity, the most large variables of the SD, Mean, maximum and median. The Personal mindset was similar. And table 8 shows humanity was higher than the other elements.

Comparison with two different groups (RQ2)

The *t* - test will be used to compare two groups same with RQ1. After the analysis (Table 9), two questions are significant ($p < 0.025$) and rejected H_0 (Null Hypothesis). Thus, the two groups have a significant difference.

<p>¹⁴ Table 9: Two-Sample <i>t</i> Test Results (RQ2) ^a</p>
<p>Hypothesis: Is there a significant difference between a group "Yes" and the group "No" in RQ2 (Q45)? ($H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$; $H_a: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)</p>

Item	Mean (Yes ^b / No ^c)	²² P(T<=t) two-tail (p<0.025)
Question B21	2.57 ^b / 2.48 ^c	0.5098837366
Question B22	2.69 ^b / 2.56 ^c	0.2836481316
Question B23	2.80 ^b / 3.04 ^c	0.07622349611
Question B24	2.00 ^b / 2.08 ^c	0.5447663397
Question B25	2.59 ^b / 2.76 ^c	0.2472535556
Question B26	1.85 ^b / 2.08 ^c	0.07537387316
Question B27	2.61 ^b / 2.56 ^c	0.6545528316
Question B28	2.33 ^b / 2.72 ^c	<u>0.006634169921</u>
Question B29	2.56 ^b / 3.00 ^c	<u>0.004690563883</u>
Question B30	3.25 ^b / 2.96 ^c	0.02648580047
Question B31	3.64 ^b / 3.76 ^c	0.3486806906
Question B32	2.91 ^b / 3.04 ^c	0.09234989773
Question B33	2.27 ^b / 2.20 ^c	0.58125085
Question B34	3.41 ^b / 3.48 ^c	0.6540942785
Humanity	3.00 ^b / 3.12 ^c	0.325881657
Environment	2.62 ^b / 2.71 ^c	0.03930619096
Personal Mindset	2.63 ^b / 2.70 ^c	0.2513516024
¹¹ ^a Showing those items found to be significantly different.		
^b Total Sample Size = 75		
^c Total Sample Size = 25		

Those two questions are a significant difference (Rejected H0) which is B28 and B29. B28 is related to personal mindset and 29 is related to the environment, related to group project and returning to school.

4.4.3 Research Question 3

There are three data points for the summary in the questionnaire section B, similar to Part A.

Summary of Part C

Table 10: General Data (Part C)

	Humanity	Environment	Personal Mindset
Mean	2.69	2.49	2.8
Std. Deviation	0.36	0.23	0.33
Minimum	2	2	2
Maximum	3.67	3.33	3.3
Kurtosis	0.45	1.03	0.1

Table 11: Part C (RQ3) Box Plot of each Institute

Table 12: Part C (RQ3) Line Chart of each Respondent

Table 10 shows results that are comparable to those in Table 6. The mean, standard deviation, and kurtosis of each group were all identical, and they were all leptokurtic as well.

Table 11 is quite similar to table 7. The statistics on personal mentality and surroundings were similar for each institute, despite the differences in size. However, there was a distinction in terms of humanity, particularly in the HKU SPACE, where the median, maximum, and range were all greater than the others.

And, as seen in Table 12, the core three components had identical statistics, with the exception of the environment being lower.

Comparison with two different groups (RQ3)

The t - test will be used to compare two groups same with RQ1 and 2. After the analysis (Table 10), four questions are significant ($p < 0.025$) and rejected H_0 (Null Hypothesis). Thus, the two groups have a significant difference.

Table 13: Two-Sample *t* Test Results (RQ3) ^a

Hypothesis: Is there a significant difference between a group "Yes" and the group "No" in RQ3 (Q46)? (H₀: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$; H_a: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)

Item	Mean (Yes ^b / No ^c)	P(T<=t) two-tail (p<0.025)
Question C35	2.29 ^b / 1.60 ^c	<u>0.02118094862</u>
Question C36	3.12 ^b / 3.60 ^c	0.08021725262
Question C37	2.09 ^b / 2.20 ^c	0.6030221961
Question C38	2.25 ^b / 2.00 ^c	0.2251176218
Question C39	3.09 ^b / 3.00 ^c	0.6324295875
Question C40	2.65 ^b / 3.40 ^c	<u>0.01537746898</u>
Question C41	2.88 ^b / 2.80 ^c	0.65591273
Question C42	3.09 ^b / 2.20 ^c	<u>0.00002409884975</u>
Question C43	2.52 ^b / 2.20 ^c	0.3833017141
Humanity	2.68 ^b / 2.80 ^c	0.4803935415
Environment	2.49 ^b / 2.60 ^c	0.2887431336
Personal Mindset	2.83 ^b / 2.27 ^c	<u>0.0001722952181</u>
^a Showing those items found to be significantly different.		
^b Total Sample Size = 95		
^c Total Sample Size = 5		

Except personal mindset, the C35, C40 and C42 were significant differences (Rejected H₀), those are related to the opportunity, school support and the protest.

The main factors Personal Mindset were a significant difference between a group "Yes" and the group "No" with all RQs, also personal mindset and environment were the main

categories which affect the students learning process and outcome, table 11 will show the comparison.

4.5 Summary

Table 11 summarises the primary factor. Table 11 displays the usual model for mediation analysis consisting of the independent variable X, the dependent variable Y, and the mediator M. Environment is M, Personal Mindset is X.

Table 14: Main factor that influence the RQ 1 to 3

Model Summary (M=aX+im)

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Standard error of the estimate	F	p-value
0.1	0.01	-0	0.18	0.96	.329

Total effect of X on Y

Effect	SE	t	p
-0.04	0.1	-0.41	.682

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	SE	t	p
-0.05	0.1	-0.48	.632

Indirect effect of X on Y

Effect	SE	t	p
0.01	0.02	0.46	.648

According to the above information, data and results, we classify four points.

- 1) RQ1 Learning Process focuses mostly on the environment (table 4), and attitude is critical for students, particularly those who believe the learning process has not altered (table 5).
- 2) RQ2 learning outcome is mostly concerned with humanity (table 8), while part B humanity is primarily concerned with B25 and B34, which are concerned with teacher assistance and preparation. And, for students who reject the RQ2, the freedom of online learning and the difficulty of completing the group project are the most crucial factors (table 9).
- 3) RQ3 regarding graduates working in this sector, the student's own perspective is the most influential aspect in determining whether or not to pursue the career (table 12 and 13). And the C40 linked to school support, the result was similar to the RQ2 (table 9), they are concerned about school support and opportunity, although some do not believe the sector would collapse; instead, they want to try this industry and discover opportunities.
- 4) Whether your CGPA is high or low, it has less to do with your own thinking; it has more to do with the environment, and it may be beneficial to relate to and connect with human beings issues more (table 14).

Chapter 5: Conclusions and Recommendations

Despite several studies on the subject from different aspects, very little study has been done on the impact of COVID-19 and Protest on hospitality education.

As a result of this research hole, the present paper examines the COVID-19 epidemic and its effect on hospitality education, especially in online educational delivery. To find out how hospitality students responded, researchers looked at a real-world example from Hong Kong. Educators' fundamental behaviours and curriculum design implications are discussed. However, the study's primary goal is to draw attention to the need for hospitality training during times of crisis. This chapter will interpret the findings and conclusions, discusses the implications for theory and practice, makes recommendations for more research, and discusses the study's relevance.

5.1 Interpretation of Results and Conclusions

As previously stated in Chapter 4, the results of all data indicate that RQ1 to 3 both rejected H0 (Null Hypothesis), as seen in 4.5 Summary, those data and information answer and interpret those RQ, hypothesis and the related factors. Also try to interpret the aims of investigating how students learn and perform in the hospitality industry under severe conditions, as well as the variables that affect this. This section will not rehash Chapter 4.5; instead, it will concentrate on the issue of that extreme consequence.

In RQ1, the highest average of the question is A11, got 3.3; Alternatively, the lowest is A3, got 2.2.

A11 demonstrates that studying online is not beneficial to the learning process, and the majority of responders picked 3 to indicate that they agree. Experience is the most traditional method for studying the environment since it influences student feelings and attempts. And the majority of A3 respondents disagree. It is comparable to A11, online learning is difficult to pay attention to, and it is also the worst experience, affecting the student's concentration and attempt to grasp but without the environment.

In RQ2, the highest average of the question is B31, got 3.7; Alternatively, the lowest is B26, got 1.9.

B31 is the most popular among students, and it ranks towards the top of the list. It said that there will be less internship and workspace for them to gain practical skills. In reality, hospitality students need a significant amount of time to practice and complete internships. They must master a variety of abilities such as F&B, Frontline system, cleaning, and so on. It takes time and practice, and if the instruction is provided online, the learner may not comprehend anything. Furthermore, B26 is associated with online studies; is it appropriate for hospitality? Most students dispute that it is comparable to the B31; they do not believe online learning is appropriate for hospitality; and it is tough to comprehend anything except the theoretical notion.

In RQ3, the highest average of the questions is C36, got 3.14; Alternatively, the lowest is C37, got 2.10.

C36 is about the graduate being able to quickly find work, and they trust it with 3.14 agree. Most respondents believe it because they feel the market will return, similar to the question of C39, which has an average of 3.09, most of them agree and believe that the Hong Kong hospitality market will return, despite the fact that C39 has the highest average. C37 also has the lowest average (2.10). C37 is connected to their belief that it is easier to obtain work as a hospitality major than as a non-hospitality major, and the majority of them do not trust and disagree. The hotel business was influenced by the COVID-19 and 2019 Protest, and they believe the industry was dropped, but they have optimism that the market will return, and that will be their opportunity.

To summarise, the online learning platform may not be appropriate for all hospitality students. The learner needs the surroundings and mood, as well as a personal attitude. Some students believe it will have little effect on their overall grades, but they are concerned about how they will operate in this field with less practice, expertise, and opportunity.

5.2 Implications for Theory and Practice

Many of the previously indicated aspects influencing the learning process and results were found to be validated in the previously mentioned research findings. This section will examine the aspects and variables associated with prior ideas and theories, as well as how to use those factors to practice the students' learning and result improvements.

According to the four-stage cyclic process (see Figure 4), to simplify ⁴ the four stages of Concrete Experience, Reflection, Abstract Conceptualisation, and Active Experimentation, those could be 1) Feeling, 2) Watching, 3) Thinking and 4) Doing.

In this case study, we recognize that most students dislike online learning because of the setting, as described in 5.1 Interpretation of Results and Conclusions. This notion is equally applicable to these four-stage cyclic processes. The cycle includes two phases of experience 'Concrete Experience and Abstract Conceptualization' and two stages of change 'Reflection and Active Experimentation' (Kolb, 1984).

When students learn online, they experience and observe it via a video or live stream. It restricts their ability to feel more and change. They abandon the material after seeing it, and they must reflect and analyse it before attempting to use it. However, although it is useful for theoretical learning, it is difficult to test it online and grasp it in practice. It is suitable to use experiential learning.

Experiential learning is important because it is an active learning process in which students "learn by doing" and reflect on their experiences. According to experiential learning, they attempt to reflect, conduct critical analysis, and synthesise. And the ability to learn from natural consequences, failures, and accomplishments, as well as the ability to make judgments (Rogers, 1969).

Students majoring in hospitality require a wide range of educational experiences, including internships, if they want to succeed in the field after graduation. Communication skills are also affected by ⁶⁹ a lack of face-to-face interaction with peers (Schleicher, 2020).

5.3 Significance of the Study

For obvious reasons, Hong Kong was the worst-hit location in the earthquake. As a result of these exceptional conditions, Hong Kong was hit hard at the beginning of the epidemic.

Unlike somewhere else in the globe, this was not the case. The epidemic caused a great deal of anxiety and suffering, and the effects lingered for quite some time. Despite the fact that Hong Kong's academics and institutions were prepared to cope with the SARS epidemic, the pandemic only increased anxiety, worry, and depression.

⁸⁸ The purpose of this research was to identify characteristics that influence the learning process, result, and post-graduate job challenges of hospitality bachelor education students in Hong Kong between 2019 and 2021, with a particular emphasis on the years 2019 and 2020. In other words, we seek to avoid another crisis or calamity, such as the war or a virus, from having a negative impact on student learning in the future. As stated at the outset, the goal of this article was to discover how students learn and perform in the hospitality sector during times of crisis, such as COVID and social unrest, in order to inform future research. We will utilise this information to improve the reactions of teachers and lecturers to the COVID 19 infections in the present and in the future.

At the least, we discovered related factors that influence the learning process and outcome in this case study, which include the broad category of humanity issues, environmental issues, and personal mindset issues. We recognize that these factors do not represent everything and that some issues may be discovered and further studied, but ⁷⁴ the purpose of this study is to inform most teachers about what they should do and prevent when the next crisis occurs and to inform the university about which factors they should consider.

Indeed, we urge that the institution place a greater emphasis on how to strengthen the online platform and maintain a positive learning environment during online classes. Even if the setting does not change, the mood will remain the same, and the school may attempt to make some games for kids to learn instead of the tedious lesson. Make an attempt to stay current by using metaverse.

5.4 Limitation and Further Research

As stated in the introduction, this case study is confined to Hong Kong and is primarily focused on students pursuing bachelor's degrees in hotel management and related fields. Furthermore, the emphasis of this case study was on the hotel industry rather than the tourist industry. Despite the fact that this case study is set in Hong Kong, it is restricted to a small number of large hotels and tourist organisations. The aforementioned restrictions had an impact on the research's comprehensive and overall study, which was not within our control.

Following the analysis, more work on the factor and hypothesis might be undertaken. Aside from attitude, human beings, and surroundings, their personal experience and the culture of the twenty-first century might be important factors. It included topics such as epistemology, pedagogy, and so on.

For further study, we suggest using phenomenology followed by Edmund Gustav Albrecht Husserl. The goal of phenomenological research is to collect data; the word used to describe this data is 'capta.' According to phenomenologists, Capta is the "data of conscious experience.", it is suitable for studying phenomena that are hard to explain and further study. Used 'capta, noema, empathy and intersubjectivity to analyse the student's personal factors that affect the learning process and outcome, may find more information (Kockelmans, 1994).

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APPENDIX A

INTERVIEW

Venue: Via by Zoom

Date: 11 to 13 December, 2021

Purpose: Explore the information, collect them for QUAN research.

Sample Number: 3

(2 Bachelor students and 1 teacher ;

Mr. Daniel Ho, Mr. Sam Wong and Dr. Ricky Chan)

**ALL SAMPLES MUST BE OF STUDENT OR TEACHER WHO STUDY OR TEACH
AFTER OR SUBSEQUENT TO 2019**

Section 1 - Introductions

Include an introduction, background information on the study, and ethical issues.

Section 2 – Questions based on RQ1 to 3

1. What are your thoughts on hospitality students acquiring knowledge? (RQ1 or 2)
2. How many times do you study or teach on online platforms? (General Q.)
3. Do you believe that online learning platforms benefit hospitality students? (RQ1 or 2)
4. Are you currently pursuing any internships or activities, and do you believe they are necessary for hospitality studies? (RQ1 or 2)
5. Do you believe that instructors or lecturers educate effectively? (RQ1 or 2)
6. Do you believe that after finishing your program, the student would have an easy time finding work in this industry? (RQ3)
7. You think how many students will pursue careers in this field after graduation? (RQ3)
8. Anything you'd want to share in relation to this subject? (Open Q.)

PLEASE NOTED: The details of content for the interview will not show in this part as the guideline said please keep the number of appendices as low as possible and no more than eight sides.

A.1. Interview Detail (Mr. Daniel Ho)

The respondent called Daniel Ho, who is a VTC School for Higher and Professional Education student, program is ⁶²Sheffield Hallam University - BSc (Hons) International Hospitality Business Management 2019 - 2020, who is the extreme case with the third class honour.

Interview

Start: 11 December, 2021; HKT: 12:01 to 12:24

Total: 23 minutes 05 seconds

Via: Zoom

A.2. Interview Detail (Dr. Ricky Chan)

The respondent called Ricky Chan, who is VTC School for Higher and Professional Education Programme Manager, mainly for Top-up bachelor degree.

Interview

Start: 12 December, 2021; HKT: 19:13 to 19:30

Total: 17 minutes 51 seconds

Via: Zoom

A.3. Interview Detail (Mr. Sam Wong)

The respondent called Sam Wong, who is a Hong Kong Polytechnic University student, programme is a Bachelor of Science (BSc) (Hons) in Hotel Management 2018 - 2022, one of the best students in STHM, received HKSAR Government Scholarship. The following information was the details of content for this interview.

Interview

Start: 13 December, 2021; HKT: 09:26 to 19:46

Total: 20 minutes 16 seconds

Via: Zoom

APPENDIX B

QUESTIONNAIRE

Topic:
Factors That Impact Hospitality Education:
A Case Study in Hong Kong Hospitality Bachelor Education During 2019 - 2021

My name is Calvin CHOI, a student at the University of Chichester - Master of Arts in Tourism and Hospitality Management. I am now conducting a survey to investigate how students learn and perform in the hospitality industry under severe conditions, as well as the variables that affect this. The purpose of the study is to explore and measure the student learning process and outcome during 2019 - 2021. This study only focused on hospitality Bachelor education students, not Tourism.

28

We respect personal data and are committed to implementing and complying with the data protection principles and the relevant provisions of the Personal Data (Privacy) Ordinance.

15

Your personal data held by us will be kept confidential but we may transfer your personal data to a data processor (e.g. printer, google drive) engaged by us to process or handle personal data on its behalf, subject to a duty of confidentiality.

31

The personal data collected will be disclosed to the following parties directly related to the above-mentioned data collection purposes:

- a) Any related to this project official educational organisation such as University, institute or college; AND
- b) Any statutory, governmental or regulatory bodies or institutions for compliance of any statutory requirements or laws.

9

You have a right to request access to, and the correction of, your personal data in accordance with the provisions of the Hong Kong Personal Data (Privacy) Ordinance (Cap. 486).

Requests for access and correction should be made by email at calvinloby@gmail.com or by letter and sent to the following address:

Rm 2407, Ching Mui House, Cheung Ching Estate, Tsing Yi, N.T., Hong Kong.

Last but not least, we will ensure participant data, including recordings, is treated confidentially and stored securely during the research project and is destroyed once I have completed the programme. We will not publish my final research or use data collected during the research project without first gaining the written consent of the London Graduate School and the organisation where the primary research was conducted.

Personal Information:

Please noted:

**PLEASE CONFIRM THAT YOU WAS THE HOSPITALITY STUDENTS
IN HONG KONG WHO STUDY IN 2019**

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1. Gender: M / F

2. What is your age: _____

3. Education (What Level are you studying now?):

- A) Sub-degree or High Diploma
- B) Bachelor Degree
- C) Master Degree or Postgraduate program
- D) Doctorate

4. Your Institute / University is: _____

5. Nationality (According to your passport or ID card)

- A) Hong Kong, China
- B) Mainland China
- C) Others, Please specific: _____

6. Your programme study period is: 20__ - 20__

7. Your average score or your CGPA: _____

(Please put X in the appropriate box)

Part A: Learning Process

3
 SD - Strongly Disagree D - Disagree
 A - Agree SA - Strongly Agree N/A - Not Applicable

A1: During the Protest and COVID-19 period, most of the classes or lessons were studied online. Compare to face-to-face studies,

	SD	D	A	SA	NA
1. studying online will let you more comfortable.					
2. studying online will be convenient to study anywhere.					
3. studying online will let you pay more attention.					
4. the instructor would respond to your inquiry if you were learning online.					
5. your classmates would discuss with you.					
6. your classmates would ask the question on the lesson.					
7. your classmates spent more time together and communicated more with you.					
8. your teacher's or lecturer's teaching material was comparable to that of an online class.					
9. your teacher's or lecturer's teaching style was comparable to that of an online class.					
10. studying online will let us lazy.					
11. studying online is not good for the learning's experience.					
12. studying online is less interaction or interplay.					
13. studying online for me is easy to use.					

3
 SD - Strongly Disagree D - Disagree
 A - Agree SA - Strongly Agree N/A - Not Applicable

A2: During the Protest and COVID-19 period, I think...

	SD	D	A	SA	NA
14. the learning atmosphere and the environment is the most important element.					
15. the learner's attitude is the most important element.					
16. the learner's attitude is more important than the classroom's atmosphere.					
17. the learner's discipline is more important, especially via online learning.					
18. the discipline in this industry is the most important factor to work in this field.					
19. my teacher's or lecturer's need more time to prepare the online lesson.					
20. my teacher's or lecturer's care less about the students.					

Part B: Learning Outcome

3
SD - Strongly Disagree D - Disagree
A - Agree SA - Strongly Agree N/A - Not Applicable

B1: During the Protest and COVID-19 period, most of the classes or lessons were studied online. Compare to face-to-face studies, ...

	SD	D	A	SA	NA
21. studying online will let you more understanding of the content or concept.					
22. studying online will let your grades plummet.					
23. studying online is good for theory lessons.					
24. studying online is good for practical lessons.					
25. your teacher's or lecturer's support was comparable to that of an online class.					
26. studying online is more suitable for hospitality subjects.					
27. studying online is more suitable for any subject.					
28. studying online would enable you more delighted owing to no need to return to school.					
29. hard to complete the group project.					

3
SD - Strongly Disagree D - Disagree
A - Agree SA - Strongly Agree N/A - Not Applicable

B2: During the Protest and COVID-19 period, I think...

	SD	D	A	SA	NA
30. the practical skills cannot be learned much.					
31. less internship and workspace for us to learn practical skills.					
32. I am lazier than before the protest and COVID.					
33. my grades plummeted when compared to before the protest.					
34. my school needs more money to maintain the online system.					

Part C: Graduates work in this field

3
SD - Strongly Disagree D - Disagree
A - Agree SA - Strongly Agree N/A - Not Applicable

C1: During the Protest and COVID-19 period, most hotels and resorts dropped the business, but....

	SD	D	A	SA	NA
35. I believe this industry have the opportunity.					
36. I believe it will be easier to find a job after I graduated.					
37. I believe it will be easier to find a job compare with other students who are not hospitality majors.					
38. I believe it will be easier to find hospitality or related job after I graduated.					
39. I believe that the Hong Kong hospitality business will rebound shortly.					
40. I believe my school will fully support me in my career after I graduated.					
41. I believe my school will completely support me to find a job, like a career orientation.					
42. I believe that protests have a greater impact on students than the virus epidemic.					
43. I believe most alumni could find the job.					

Overall: During the Protest and COVID-19 period in Hong Kong...

	Yes	No
44. I believe the learning process has changed between prior and current years.		
45. I believe the learning outcome has changed between prior and current years.		
46. I believe there is certainly a difference in the capacity of graduates to work in the field and obtain jobs between past and current years.		

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